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SIMULATION AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL IN THE ENGINEERING CURRICULUM

S. C. Cooke¹
Ansys Granta
Cambridge, UK

D. Cebon
University of Cambridge Engineering Department
Cambridge, UK

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ABSTRACT

Simulation has become increasingly important in professional engineering over the last few decades. In undergraduate education, simulation tools are often taught in advanced-level classes to equip students to use them in industry. However, simulation is not widely used as a pedagogical tool itself within engineering education. This paper examines the current evidence base for simulation as an educational tool and discusses the output of a student internship at Ansys Granta focusing on this topic. An undergraduate student intern from the University of Cambridge evaluated the potential use of Ansys Discovery Live software to support a first-year undergraduate engineering curriculum. Worked examples across the fields of structures, mechanics and fluids were tackled, and Discovery Live was used both to attempt to replicate these examples and to extend them. This qualitative study found that, for the examples where Discovery Live was found able to support the curriculum, i.e. able to accurately simulate the problems tackled, it provided significant benefits to the student. These benefits included visualisation of problems, the ability to tackle more complex systems, interrogation of the assumptions and idealisations inherent in many hand calculations, and the possibility to either supplement or replace physical lab experiments where required. This paper also proposes a cost-benefit approach to evaluate the wider inclusion of simulation tools as teaching tools in undergraduate engineering curricula and consider the trade-off against instructor workload to highlight types of undergraduate engineering teaching where simulation could provide most benefit.

¹ *Corresponding Author*
S. C. Cooke
susannah.cooke@ansys.com

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Current knowledge

Modelling and simulation tools are of increasing interest for undergraduate engineering teaching due to their prevalent usage in both research and industry. There have been a number of individual studies of undergraduate engineering teaching and learning using modelling and simulation tools across the engineering undergraduate curriculum [1,2,3]. Across multiple studies, benefits to student learning outcomes are reported [4] but difficulties include students' perceptions of simulation tools and the steepness of the learning curve to use them effectively.

1.2 Ansys Granta opportunity

Granta Design Ltd, a leader in the field of undergraduate Materials education, was acquired in 2019 by Ansys, Inc, a leader in multiphysics engineering simulation. An opportunity therefore arose for a student internship at Granta evaluating the potential of existing Ansys simulation tools to be used effectively in undergraduate teaching. Discovery Live was chosen as the most suitable tool for this study due to its easy learning curve thanks to its automatic meshing and real-time simulation capabilities.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Overview

The internship was a 12-week project, including company induction during the first week and project reporting in the final two weeks. There were thus approximately nine weeks of simulation work. The intern was given a computer containing a GPU capable of supporting Ansys Discovery Live. The project supervisors did not have any previous knowledge of Discovery Live, or any personal access to the software during the internship. The intern was at the end of his 2nd year in the undergraduate Engineering course at the University of Cambridge, and had not previously used any simulation software either as part of the course or for personal interest. Supervision meetings were weekly, with regular self-reporting required from the intern.

2.2 Goals

The project plan was for the intern to self-learn Discovery Live and use it to tackle a number of analytical engineering problems taken from the 1st and 2nd year material of the University of Cambridge Engineering degree course. The intern was therefore already familiar with the analytical solutions of these problems, but was required to simulate the problems using Discovery Live and to extract answers to the problems from simulation. These simulation results could then be compared to the analytical answers. Initial goals were to complete 8-10 problems of this type across a range of standard mechanical, fluids, thermodynamics and vibration problems, identify problems that could not be simulated in Discovery Live, and create documentation for each successful simulation. Additional goals at the end of the project were to identify where problem sets could be extended or deepened for further learning using the simulations developed. There was also a task to look at 'learning types' (lectures, labs, etc) and suggest where each simulated model could add most value.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Self-learning of Ansys Discovery Live

Having been provided with Discovery Live, the first goal was for the intern to self-learn the software. It was hoped that a typical undergraduate student with no previous experience of simulation tools could teach themselves to use Discovery Live, given its automatic meshing and real-time simulation. This goal was mostly achieved. The student intern was able to grasp the vast majority of tools and capabilities within a week using the software help, online resources and template models available. The only issues that arose were around technical terminology used within Discovery Live which was beyond the understanding of the student but was required for successful simulations – e.g. ‘slip symmetry’ in fluid dynamics.

3.2 Problems Attempted

A total of ten problems were simulated successfully: four in fluid dynamics, three in structural analysis, and one each in the areas of materials, thermodynamics and modal analysis. A further six problems from the same teaching areas were considered and rejected, some because Discovery Live could not simulate them fully, others because the simulation would be too simple to add any understanding.

An example of the outcomes from one simulation shows the typical scope of work. This structural analysis problem considered a load on a pin-jointed truss as shown in Figure 1, and required use of virtual work and a displacement diagram to solve analytically. Using Discovery Live, a slender truss with rigid joints was simulated, as this was considerably easier than including pin joints and provided an additional learning outcome. The vertical displacement of node C as reported by Discovery Live was within 0.07% of the analytical virtual work solution. The intern was also able to extract vector displacements for each point in the simulation and thus create a ‘simulated’ displacement diagram as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 1. Analytical problem (above) and Discovery Live simulation highlighting displacement (below)

Fig. 2. Overlaid analytical and simulated displacement diagrams, to scale

The student intern also created a short 2-page 'case study' for this problem, with instructions on setting up the simulation, results to be expected and sample plots. The benefits of adding a simulation aspect to this analytical problem were threefold, as reported by the intern and observed by the supervisors: firstly, an animated visualisation of the problem aided intuitive understanding of structural mechanics, deformations and support movement; secondly, the ability to gain solutions which agree with the analytical methods reinforced the understanding of those methods; and thirdly, the process of setting up the simulation problem highlighted assumptions and areas in which the intern's physical understanding of the problem were weaker.

3.3 Additional Learning Outcomes

Across all ten problems that were simulated, the intern reported additional learning points which were not within the scope of the original analytical problems. In some cases these were learning about simulation, as in the case of boundary conditions, but in many cases they concerned real physical aspects of the problem which may be mentioned in introductory engineering courses but are usually assumed to be unimportant when solving these problems analytically. These included mixing lengths for fluid dynamics problems, spring masses in modal vibration problems, and various assumptions within classical beam theory such as slenderness of beams.

3.4 Project Limitations

Although the student chosen for this internship was representative of a standard 2nd year undergraduate engineer, there are factors which are likely to have given him an advantage over the average student using these tools for the first time. Most importantly, the intern had regular access to supervisors who, while not familiar with Discovery Live, had previous exposure to other simulation tools and were able to assist in identifying setup errors or erroneous assumptions in his simulations. The intern also likely had higher motivation to learn simulation since this was a paid internship rather than an extra thing to learn within the undergraduate curriculum.

3.5 Cost/Benefit Approach to Including Simulation in Curricula

The scope of this project was not just to assess the additional learning that could be supported by adding simulation to undergraduate teaching; it was also to assess the practical challenges of requiring students to use a simulation tool such as Discovery Live in introductory courses. This study was not aiming to quantitatively assess the learning benefits to the intern or, by extension, the potential for benefit to the wider student body. However, through the intern's self-reporting of his learning, the study qualitatively highlighted benefits in the areas of visualisation, understanding of assumptions and the ability to study complex problems. Other studies have attempted more rigorous measurement of student outcomes following the use of simulation or modelling [4], which similarly to this study report benefits to the students when they are adequately supported by well-designed documentation or active supervision. In order to decide whether to include the use of simulation tools in a curriculum, the educator effort required to support students in this way must be weighed against the benefits that students will gain.

At the end of this project, the intern was asked to reflect on which types of teaching he felt the extended problem set would best fit. He personally felt the use of simple visualisations in lectures or more detailed ‘virtual lab’ projects in labs were areas of introductory engineering teaching where significant benefit could be gained. Reflecting on these and other types of teaching, we propose a simple cost-benefit analysis to conceptualise the trade-off between teaching effort and student benefit, as visualised in Figure 3(a). The points on this chart are placed qualitatively, based on the benefits reported by the intern and the supervisors’ understanding of the likely workload required to properly introduce simulation to each type of teaching. The top right quadrant of this figure is the area in which the educator effort required is reasonable to achieve the benefits. As can be seen, with no available resources for the educator to draw on, we believe the only teaching type which fits in this quadrant is capstone design projects, where a significant learning curve is acceptable and students can use software with which their supervisors are unfamiliar. However, Figure 3(b) shows a hypothetical situation in which other types of teaching become tractable in terms of educator effort required. Arrows represent the creation of resources which educators can draw on to reduce individual effort required, thus making it reasonable to consider introducing simulation into these types of teaching.

Figs. 3(a) and 3(b). Illustration of a possible cost-benefit analysis to assess educator effort required to introduce simulation into a teaching type (x-axis) vs. reported benefit to students of doing so (y-axis).

Examples of such resources could range from simple pre-made animations to aid visualisation in lectures, to lab experiment resources with full simulation models and worked guidance for demonstrators. We believe that the creation of these resources, and their availability within the wider academic community, are key to enabling the use of simulation and modelling tools within undergraduate engineering education.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project shows that it is possible for an undergraduate engineering student to gain significant benefits from the addition of simulation to a traditional problem set across multiple areas of fundamental engineering teaching. However, it is important to identify the areas where greatest benefit can be gained, and how students using simulation can best be supported without significantly increasing teaching workload.

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